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TEACH DIGITAL AND LEARN DIGITALLY (AN INNOVATIVE TOOL: SMART SOFTWARE)

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Abstract

Objective- Under a new teaching method called “engagement” students are urged to engage with the real world, analyses everything that happens in different life spheres. Instead of conventional teaching methods, students were taken to visit local businesses where they were able to witness how the knowledge that they were learning applied to the real world. The idea is to get students engaged and to connect their learning to the real world. If teachers can show them how what they are teaching connects to the real world then their own brain cells are going to connect them and associate them. Increasingly, nations are recognizing that improving education is the best way to increase wealth, enhance health, and maintain peace. Much of what children learn in schools today was designed for the era of paper-and-pencil. We need to update curriculum for the digital age. Community is becoming digitally savvy and students want to explore via all digital medium be it desktop, Laptop, Tablet, Mobile etc. 2015 was the digital year where it was found that in India 350 million users are on internet, 134 million are active media users, and 97 million are mobile users (PWC,2016).Our Indian education industry is lacking in providing a better techno savvy tool for high-tech student other than smart board and few online tools. This paper tries to explore how technology can bring innovative inclusion in digital market for millennial, by developing innovative smart software in the field of education for students. The paper will bring an extensive research work in understanding the technology used in education Industry by qualitative as well as quantitative methodology and thus an innovative idea will be generated keeping in mind Indian education sector and Indian education need.

Design / Methodology/ Approach-The present research paper is conceptualized and is based on secondary data collected from various resources like books, news papers, management journals and internet. In order to have a practical experience, this paper has also analyzed successful implementation of Digital means of education at various levels.

Findings- Growing up with unprecedented access to technology has changed the way young people, "digital natives," communicate, interact, process information, and learn Thus, many new teachers entering 21st century classrooms are digital natives teaching digital natives, although future teachers may hold strong positive beliefs about technology and may be proficient with a variety of software . They just need to develop a systematic understanding of the technology, subject matter, pedagogy, and how these aspects work together"

Limitations-Present research is conceptualized and based on secondary data; research could have been more authenticated if it would have been based on primary data.

Practical implications-This paper can inspire educators and researcher of their fields for bringing certain changes in their existing Education system and pedagogy for better future education. By implementing innovative techniques or strategies, education sector can become more competitive and robust.

Originality/Value- The paper includes practical examples of organizations following different education techniques and also includes literature review about existing and upcoming teaching technologies, which promotes unique and interesting contributions in education system.

Key words: Education, SMART-SOFTWARE, Technology

Literature Review:

In the years ahead, the declining cost of computation will make digital technologies accessible to nearly everyone in all parts of the world, from inner-city neighborhoods in the United States to rural villages in developing nations. These new technologies have the potential to fundamentally transform how and what people learn throughout their lives. Just as advances in biotechnologies made possible the “green revolution” in agriculture, new digital technologies make possible a

“learning revolution” in education. To take full advantage of new technologies, we need to fundamentally rethink our approaches to learning and education— and our ideas of how new technologies can support them.

Visualization is an especially good teaching strategy for reading and literacy teachers. We just need to understand how to use visualization to help students illustrate mental images from a portion of text that is read aloud. Computers, tablets, digital cameras, videoconferencing technology and GPS devices can enhance a student’s learning experience. Possible uses of classroom technology include using video games to teach math and foreign languages, leveraging Skype to communicate with classrooms or guest speakers from around the world, or multimedia projects that allow students to explore subject matter using film, audio and even software they create.

Under a new teaching method called “engagement” students are urged to engage with the real world, analyse everything that happens in different life spheres. Instead of conventional teaching methods, students were taken to visit local businesses where they were able to witness how the knowledge that they were learning applied to the real world. The idea is to get students engaged and to connect their learning to the real world. If teachers can show them how what they are teaching connects to the real world then their own brain cells are going to connect them and associate them.

It is a kind of liberating creativity that makes teaching exciting and fun, engages students, and— most critical—helps students find the passion and resources necessary to design a better life for themselves and others. Industry uses a set of cutting edge tools to stimulate creativity and innovation. Beyond Words, the tools include playful games and visual exercises that can easily be used in the classroom. Toys have always been an important part of a child's spirited learning and holistic development. Edutainment chains aspects of education and entertainment into products and experiences that seek to improve learning by making it not just trouble-free but also enjoyable. Games and learning enjoy an association that predates digital technology by thousands of years.

The Indian Toy Industry has witnessed a lot of changes over the last few years with regard to categories of toys, innovation, eye-catching design and other aspects. The revamping of the toy Industry has shown remarkable evolution & extension in the domestic market. The budding attentiveness among parents in India has led to the growth in toys market and predominantly educational toys and games made of plastics and cardboard that offers creativity and lead to the development of the brain of the child. The extent to which contemporary developments require changes in how we teach and how students learn. So I thought of giving the concept of Teach Digital and Learn Digitally. Increasingly, nations are recognizing that improving education is the best way to increase wealth, enhance health, and maintain peace. Much of what children learn in schools today was designed for the era of paper-and-pencil. We need to update curriculum for the digital age.

We need to fundamentally reorganize school classrooms. Instead of a centralized-control model (with a teacher delivering information to a roomful of students), we should take a more entrepreneurial approach to learning. Students can become more active and independent learners, with the teacher serving as consultant, not chief executive. Instead of dividing up the curriculum into separate disciplines (math, science, social studies, language), we should focus on themes and projects that cut across the disciplines, taking advantage of the rich connections among different domains of knowledge. Instead of dividing students according to age, we should encourage students of all ages to work together on projects, enabling them to learn from one another (and to learn by teaching one another). Instead of dividing the school day into hour-long slices, we should let students work on projects for extended periods of time, enabling them to follow through more deeply and meaningfully on the ideas that arise in the course of their work.

Schools must prepare students with the new skills and ideas that are needed for living and working in a digital society. The proliferation of digital technologies has accentuated the need for creative thinking in all aspects of our lives, and has also provided tools that can help us improve and reinvent ourselves. Throughout the world, computing and communications technologies are sparking a new entrepreneurial spirit, the creation of innovative products and services, and increased productivity. The importance of a well-educated, creative citizenry is greater than ever before.

In the digital age, learning can and must become a daylong and lifelong experience. National education initiatives should aim to improve learning opportunities not only in schools, but also in homes, community centers, museums, and workplaces. In Denmark, for example, the Ministry of Education joined with the Ministry of Business and Industry to create Learning Lab Denmark, a new research lab that studies learning in all settings, in all stages of life. In the years ahead, the Internet will open up new learning opportunities, enabling new types of “knowledge building communities” in which children (and adults) around the globe collaborate on projects and learn from one another. In addition to rethinking our approaches to learning and education, we also need to rethink the technologies that we provide to young people.

Most of today’s computers were designed primarily for use by adults in the workplace. We need to develop a new generation of computer technologies worthy of the next generation of children. It’s not enough just to make computers faster; we need to develop new types of computers. Today’s youth are ready and eager to do more with computers. We need to provide the hardware and software that will enable them to do so.

These new technologies might look very different from traditional computers. For example, a family of “programmable bricks”: tiny computers embedded inside children’s building blocks (Martin et al. 2000; Resnick et al. 1996). With these bricks, children can build computational power directly into their physical-world constructions, using the programmable bricks to control motors, receive information from sensors, and even communicate with one another.

The shift in focus from “information” to “knowledge” is an improvement. But I prefer a different conception: the “Creative Society.” As I see it, success in the future will be based not on how much we know, but on our ability to think and act creatively. The proliferation of digital technologies has accentuated the need for creative thinking in all aspects of our lives, and has also provided tools that can help us improve and reinvent ourselves. Throughout the world, computing and communications technologies are sparking a new entrepreneurial spirit, the creation of innovative products and services, and increased productivity

The newest student generation, sometimes called “New Millennial Learners,”¹ is growing up surrounded by digital media and technologies. For them, the ability to access information and communication technologies (ICT) is increasingly important to effectively participate in the economic, political, and social aspects of the so-called knowledge society. Digital literacies, which include information literacy, media literacy, and ICT literacy,³ have been highlighted as a pillar of “21st century skills” in many influential international initiatives.

For many parents and educators, the appeal of games and digital media for learning centers on the novelty of the idea that activities that engage young people so wholly can be educational, too. Game-based learning, on the other hand, applies to using actual digital video games as a classroom tool— although traditional non-electronic role playing and board games work exactly the same way, but perhaps not as efficiently—and there are a slew of video games, digital applications (“apps”), and adaptive software platforms that can be used for instruction. Some are great, while others are not so helpful.

Game-based learning in the classroom can encourage students to understand subject matter in context, as part of a system. In contrast to memorization, drilling, and quizzing, which is often criticized because the focus is on facts in isolation, games force players to interact with problems in ways that take relationships into account. The content becomes useful insofar as it plays a part in a larger multimodal system. The game does one thing. The player responds with another. In order to beat the game, the player needs to master the system.

The way we understand the expectations and promises of today’s game-based approaches will have a long term impact on how we imagine and implement them in the future. It’s critical that teachers, parents, and administrators understand not only the research, but also the way corporations, foundations, and research organizations are thinking about games and learning. There are big players involved in researching the benefits of game-based learning in schools. Companies and foundations like the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, the MacArthur Foundation, the Educational Testing Service (ETS), Pearson, Inc., Electronic Arts (EA), and the Entertainment Software Association (ESA) are all involved. Each has a different role in the matter and teachers have different perceptions of what those roles are.

Digital storytelling connects students to content in ways that they are accustomed to consuming information. Students watch, share, and comment on snippets of videos from TV and movies. They make their own videos and post them to online forums. In fact, the video sharing site YouTube is now serving more than two billion videos per day (Chapman, 2010). The viral video is the cultural currency of today's youth.

Growing up with unprecedented access to technology has changed the way young people, "digital natives," communicate, interact, process information, and learn. Thus, many new teachers entering 21st century classrooms are digital natives teaching digital natives, although future teachers may hold strong positive beliefs about technology and may be proficient with a variety of software. They just need to develop a systematic understanding of the technology, subject matter, pedagogy, and how these aspects work together"

Conclusion :

Information and Communications Technologies are changing the world in which students live.

As technology becomes more pervasive, it is placing considerable pressure on systems to keep up and develop necessary tools to ensure both quality and equity in learning resources and experiences for students. While the potential for technology to improve learning is real, particular trends or products still run considerable risks of being 'oversold and underused.' With more time for reflection, students may be more likely to draw on their broader backgrounds in an online forum than a face-to-face class. Multiple digital images can better demonstrate diversity across time and place than text.

The key benefits of using digital tools and technologies identified were increased efficiency, relevance, and interactivity; enhanced course content; and student engagement, collaboration, and reflection. A number of challenges involved with using digital tools and technologies and reasons for non-adoption were also identified; the main themes that emerged were digital literacy, impact on other aspects of teaching and learning, limited student use, time and effort, and IT support.

The digital tools and technologies that participants aspire to use in the future can be categorized as augmented reality, better quality equipment, increased access and those directly supporting teaching and learning. With regard to the teaching and learning environment in which digital technologies and tools are used, aspirations related to research, knowledge sharing, collaboration, digital literacy and critical thinking.

References :

Digital Storytelling : A tool for teaching and Learning in the Youtube Generation

Mind / Shift Guide to Digital Games + Learning By Jordan Shapiro, ET AL

Bell, L., & Bull, G. (2010). Digital video and teaching. *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education*, 10(1), 1-6.

Bull, G. L., & Bell, L. (Eds.). (in press). *Teaching with digital video: Watch, analyze, create*. Eugene, OR: International Society for Technology in Education.